

National Evolutionary Synthesis Center

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Reporting Requirements for NESCent

The information you provide to us by reporting is vital for evaluating our effectiveness at fostering cross-disciplinary research, generating lasting collaborations, promoting scientific productivity, and producing lasting scientific impacts. We also want to ensure that we are attracting and supporting disciplinary, geographic, and demographic diversity. These data are utilized both internally and also reported to the National Science Foundation. If you have specific questions about your reporting responsibilities do not hesitate to contact the Assistant Director of Science Craig McClain at cmclain@nescent.org. Your reporting responsibilities to NESCent throughout the lifespan of your NESCent-sponsored project include:

1. Demographics

All participants are required to provide demographic information that we will use confidentially for our reporting to the National Science Foundation. We expect PI's to encourage group participants to report this data. We ask for demographic data relating to gender, ethnicity, race, disability, and citizenship, job title, institution (this is done through our administrative database, <http://nead.nescent.org>) so that:

- We can gauge whether our programs and other opportunities in science and technology are fairly reaching and benefitting everyone regardless of demographic category;
- We can ensure that those in under-represented groups have the same knowledge of and access to programs, meetings, vacancies, and other research and educational opportunities as everyone else; and
- We can monitor involvement of international investigators or students in work we support.

2. Public Summary

We ask you to write a public summary for our website and for reporting back to the National Science Foundation. These summaries are an opportunity for you to describe and promote your work to interested outside readers — from scientists outside your field, to friends, family, and the media. The summaries should be 150-400 words in length and geared to a reasonably educated member of the public, i.e. a "NPR audience." They should describe your research questions, how you plan to address them, and ultimately the importance of the work (why should your audience care?). These summaries may be reviewed and modified by our current Communications Director for clarity as needed. To upload your summary, log into www.nead.nescent.org and enter text into the public summary field in your project. For more information please contact NESCent's Communications Manager Robin Smith at rsmith@nescent.org

3. Status Reports

PI's are required to submit status reports after each meeting (this is done through our administrative database, <http://nead.nescent.org>). The following information is included in each report:

- List of project leaders and participants
- Goals of the project, including the specific goals of the workshop meeting
- Summary of activities and discussion at the meeting
- Plans for any follow-up activities emerging from the meeting
- Anticipated outcomes and products (e.g. databases, papers, proposals, other meetings)

4. Surveys

We also ask participants to complete surveys after each meeting to ensure that the center is providing a high level of administrative and informatics support to your group. Our Assistant Director of Science Craig McClain will send an email to you after each meeting with a link to the survey.

5. Products

PI's are required to inform the center of articles, books, grants, software, and databases produced from NESCent supported projects. Please do so by entering them into our administrative database (<http://nead.nescent.org>)

- Data or datasets, software, published books and scholarly articles generated or created by a NESCent fellow or through a project or meeting supported by NESCent must appropriately and conspicuously acknowledge NESCent and the National Science Foundation. The following citation may be used in this regard: *Supported by the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center (NESCent), NSF #EF-0905606.*

6. Press Coverage

As your group prepares to publish its work, please contact us in advance of publication. Our communications office is eager to work with you to develop press releases to highlight your results, which we will write and distribute to your university news office(s) on your behalf. For a sample of previous press releases or to discuss possibilities for making your work available to the wider public, please contact NESCent's Communications Manager Robin Smith at rsmith@nescent.org